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Why The Economy of Ho Chi Minh City is Important to the Vietnamese Economy? A Study Based on Inter-Regional Relations

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Abstract:

This study is based on the concept of inter-regional analysis to describe the internal structure of the industry and interdisciplinary as well as the internal structure of the region and the inter-region of Ho Chi Minh City (HCMC) for the rest of Vietnam (ROV). Theoretically for a country, there are often industries that are of relative importance higher than more compared to other sectors in the economy through the power of dispersion and sensitivity of dispersion indexes. The concept of interregional analysis was concretized by Isard (1951) and concretized by Harry W. Richardson (1973) and Miyazawa, K. (1976) and it is considered as an important tool in research regional economic research. Similar to industry, a region or province has its own importance (by industry specific) and a certain region may have more pervasive importance to the national economy than other regions/provinces. This study is based on the inter-regional input - output table of Vietnam between HCMC and ROV, 2012 and 2016 with 55 sectors (Appendix 1)

Key Words: HCMC, final demand, final products, input – output, interregional, multiplier, Vietnam

I. Introduction

Ho Chi Minh City (HCMC), also known by the popular old name Saigon, is the largest city in Vietnam and a megacity in the near future. This is also the center of economy, politics, culture, entertainment and education in Vietnam. Ho Chi Minh City is a centrally run city belonging to a special urban type of Vietnam. Located in the transition zone between the Southeast and the Southwest, this city currently has 16 districts, 1 city and 5 districts, with a total area of 2,095 km² (809 sq mi). According to the preliminary census results in 2021, the city's population is 9,166,800 people (9.3% of Vietnam's population), the average population density is 4,375 people/km² (the highest in the country). However, the actual population of this city in 2018 is nearly 14 million people (if we include unregistered residents). HCMC's GRDP contributes over 22% of Vietnam's GDP and 27% of the country's total budget revenue. GRDP per capita in 2020 is estimated at 6,328 USD/person.

In 1941 Wassily Leontief presented a fairly complete inter - industry balance model (also known as input output table) to analyze the economic structure of the United States with the famous study "Structure of the American Economy, ". Economic structure in this study is understood in this sense. The science of regional economics is based on the extended application of the I/O model by W. Isard and M. Peck (1951, 1954). Since then, it has been perfected by many famous economists such as Richardson Harry W (1973), Miyazawa (1966), Miller, R.E., and P.D. Blair (1985); Sonis, Hewings (1998).

Inter-regional I-O models have been applied in many empirical studies to address a wide range of policy issues and to analyze their impacts on other regions. For example, Brian et al. (2006) described current uses of inter-country I-O models and their applications to understanding a range of policy issues, such as global value chains and production fragmentation, technology flows, productivity and determinants of growth, industrial ecology and sustainable development. Fernando and Urena (2006) introduced a new method of regionalization and disaggregation which takes into account the gross value added of each sector in every region and the transport infrastructure used by these regions.

To analyze the inter-regional feedback effects and the degree to which change originating in one region has capacity to influence activity levels in another region, Bui et al. (2000, 2013, 2017) applied an interregional I-O model on a case study of HoChiMinh City and the rest of Vietnam. Harries et al. (1998) separated the Lincoln County into the Caliente area and the rest of Lincoln County. Following procedures outlined by Robinson (1997), Holland (1991), and Robinson and Lark (1993), Harries et al. (1998) used an inter-regional model to give local decision makers an idea of potential socio-economic and fiscal impacts from changes in local economic activity.

Inter-regional I-O models are also used to estimate the damages and losses by unscheduled events, such as earthquakes, flood, and other major natural disasters. Okuyama et al. (1999, 2002) applied a sequential inter-industry model to assess the impacts of the Great Hanshin earthquake in such a way to enable transportation into the I-O framework. Other recent studies using the inter-regional I-O model include Allan et al. (2004), Zhang (2007), Patrick and Wang (2007), and Rey (1999).

This study is based on the inter-regional input - output table of Vietnam between HCMC and ROV, 2012 and 2016 with 55 sectors

II. Methodology

One of the important contributions of regional federation models is the development of the regional input - output model into the Inter-regional input - output model. Along with the econometric models, the social accounting matrix (SAM), the general equilibrium model (CGE), the interregional input - output model is considered as a competitor in choosing the appropriate models for researchers and policy makers (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Inter - regional effects

Note: ΔVA is the change of value added

W. Leontief's basic relations take the form:

$$X = (I - A)^{-1} \cdot Y \tag{1}$$

Where: X is a vector/matrix of output, I is identify matrix, Y is a vector/matrix of final demand. In the inter-regional input – output system, matrix A includes sub – matrices as follow:

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} A_{vv} & A_{vc} \\ A_{cv} & A_{cc} \end{bmatrix} \tag{2}$$

With: A_{vv} is intra – intermediate input matrix of region V , A_{cv} is a matrix that element of this matrix present region V used products of region C as intermediate inputs, A_{vc} is a matrix that region C used products of region V as intermediate inputs, A_{cc} is intra – intermediate input matrix of region C .

The vector of output includes output of region V (X_v) and output of region C (X_c)

$$X = \begin{bmatrix} X_v \\ X_c \end{bmatrix} \tag{3}$$

Matrix final demand Y can be expressed as:

$$Y = \begin{bmatrix} Y_{VV} & Y_{VC} \\ Y_{CV} & Y_{CC} \end{bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

Where: Y_{VV} is a matrix of final demand that products of region V are used products by itself, Y_{VC} is a matrix that final demand of region C are used products of region C, Y_{CV} is a matrix that products of region C are used by final demand of region V, Y_{CC} is a matrix of final demand that products of region C are used by itself

Put:

$$B = (I - A)^{-1} = \begin{bmatrix} B_{VV} & B_{VC} \\ B_{CV} & B_{CC} \end{bmatrix} \quad (5)$$

Equation (1) can be rewritten as:

$$X = B.Y \quad (6)$$

In inter – regional input – output system the output requirement B_V and B_C were defined as below:

$$B_V = B_{VV} + B_{CV}$$

$$B_C = B_{CC} + B_{VC}$$

B_{VV} and B_{CC} called enlarge Leontief inverse matrices, these includes *multiplier effects (ME)* and *interregional feedback effects (IFE)*, B_{CV} and B_{VC} are *spillover effects*

$$ME_V = (I - A_{VV})^{-1} \quad (7)$$

$$ME_C = (I - A_{CC})^{-1} \quad (8)$$

$$IEF_V = B_{VV} - ME_V \quad (9)$$

$$IEF_C = B_{CC} - ME_C \quad (10)$$

Call: v_V and v_C are value added coefficient vectors of region V and region C

Multiply the two sides of relationship (6) by $v = (v_V, v_C)$ we have::

$$V = (V_V, V_C) = v.B.Y \quad (11)$$

vB is called value added multipliers

$v_V.ME_V$ present as *multiplier effects* on value added induced by final demand of region V

$v_V.IEF_V$ present the *inter – regional effects* on value added induced by production of region C (when regional V use products of region C will induce to production of region C, in the production process region C use products of region V for intermediate input lead to spread to output and value added of region V)

$v_C.B_{CV}$ present *spillover effects* on value added due to final demand of region V induce to emission of region C

$v_v.ME_v + v_v.IEF_v + v_c.BC_v$ is total value added multipliers of region V that induced by final demand of region V and production of region C

III. Case studies

Theoretically for a country, there are often industries that are of relative importance more than compared to other sectors in the economy through the indicators of power and sensitivity of dispersion. The concept of interregional analysis Isard (1951) introduced and concretized by Harry W. Richardson (1973) and Miyazawa, K. (1976) concretized and it is considered as an important tool in research on regional economy.

The initial look in Table 1 shows that the structure of intermediate costs compared to the production value of the 2 periods that the input - output tables 2012 and 2016 represent has not changed much, the ratio of intermediate costs to output of the 2016 I/O table is 67%, this rate in the 2012 I/O table is only 67.8%; However, a closer look at the structure of HCMC's economy through the power and sensitivity of dispersion indexes in the two periods can see output requirements of the period 2015 - 2020 (I/O table 2016 as representative) is much lower than the period 2010 - 2015 (I/O table 2012 is representative) quite a lot (-52%); Output requirements of input - output table, 2012 is about 2.97, the output requirements of input - output table, 2016 is only 1.41. In addition, many industries have quite a lot of changes in the degree of spillover. In the past, the agro-processing industry group had a higher spillover index than the general average (>1), but in the current period, this group of industries is no longer diffused. The extent of the spread of industries to the economy is quite low, showing that Ho Chi Minh City's economy is becoming more and more comprehensive.

Table 1. Power and sensitivity of dispersion indexes of HCMC for the period 2010 -2015 and the period 2015-2020 (times)

	2007		2012	
	BL	FL	BL	FL
1	0.729	1.762	0.843	0.71
2	0.967	0.541	0.983	0.9
3	0.73	0.47	0.821	0.72
4	0.408	0.577	0.821	0.71
5	0.934	0.53	0.914	0.75
6	0.854	1.722	0.878	1.11
7	1.843	2.009	1.047	0.72
8	1.166	0.55	0.875	0.8
9	1.049	0.376	0.819	0.76
10	1.099	0.491	1.303	1.09
11	1.082	0.745	0.831	0.74
12	1.213	0.594	1.255	1.05
13	1.266	0.61	0.851	0.85
14	0.791	0.363	0.913	0.72
15	1.156	0.341	0.877	0.71
16	1.401	1.671	1.009	0.76
17	1.238	0.489	0.883	0.73
18	1.26	0.769	0.864	0.73
19	1.0648	0.793061	0.961	0.76
20	1.274932	1.742118	1.175	1.41
21	1.041157	0.454916	1.153	0.8
22	1.288045	4.615123	0.828	0.8
23	1.398719	4.25765	0.952	0.78
24	0.94922	0.822071	1.052	1.67
25	1.445264	1.240001	0.983	1.24
26	1.007432	0.582976	1.248	1.03
27	1.418499	1.375128	1.283	1.04
28	1.150321	3.771053	0.941	1.01
29	1.154757	1.193129	0.972	0.76

30	1.058311	1.468659	1.496	1.37
31	1.24014	0.623366	1.029	0.79
32	1.461078	1.001442	1.12	1.24
33	1.22625	0.765354	1.098	0.71
34	1.284369	0.571091	1.064	0.79
35	1.301975	0.823456	1.313	1
36	1.151293	0.437551	1.019	0.73
37	1.175647	1.206367	0.964	1.37
38	1.055368	1.43171	0.787	0.94
39	0.7144	0.530373	0.888	0.83
40	1.145333	0.42983	1.239	0.98
41	0.629289	3.226665	1.006	3.88
42	1.062887	0.56991	0.897	0.76
43	0.822878	1.152255	0.947	1.98
44	0.628489	0.623003	0.856	0.72
45	0.538046	0.395559	0.986	0.77
46	1.111583	0.440565	1.039	0.83
47	0.48302	0.592623	0.921	0.91
48	0.416866	0.895967	1.007	1.6
49	0.511623	0.336665	1.176	1.42
50	0.516869	0.336665	0.863	0.71
51	0.584252	0.336665	0.833	0.71
52	0.51728	0.336665	0.961	0.74
53	0.770287	0.336665	1.175	0.71
54	0.579229	0.336665	0.921	0.73
55	0.632166	0.336665	1.062	1.98
	2.97		1.41	

Table 2 shows that the induced impacts of HCMC and ROV when the production of one region spreads to the output of another region is similar. However, the induced impacts of one unit of final demand of HCMC stimulate the output of ROV much higher than the opposite side (0.511 and 0.06 = 8.7 times). Notably, the demand for domestic imports and foreign import to produce a unit of final products of ROV is higher than that of HCMC. This implies that when ROV wants increase production, it will not only induce to output that region, but also stimulate import and HCMC's production

Table 2. Interregional structure between HCMC and ROV (times)

	HCMC	ROV
1. Domestic output requirement	2.97	2.146
In which:		
Multiplier effects	2.45	2.07
Interregional feedback effects	0.01	0.01
Spillover effects	0.51	0.06
2. Import Requirement	0.298	0.433

Source: Calculating of authors

Considering the three regions of HCMC and the ROV in Table 3, it shows that when the final demand inside HCMC (including final consumption of HCMC residents, investment and export) increases to 100 dong, the spillover the value added in Ho Chi Minh City is about 89% and 11% spreads to other regions. In particular, consumption of people in Ho Chi Minh City will spread to value added in other regions of the country by 17%, while investment and export of Ho Chi Minh City will spread to value added in other regions. the rest of the country is 8.8% and 8.7%. This is a very high spillover rate, showing the importance of Ho Chi Minh City's economy to the national economy.

Table 3. Value added induced by domestic final demand of three regions (times)

Value added induced by	HCMC			ROV		
	C	I	E	C	I	E
Southwest of Vietnam	0.063	0.024	0.026	0.042	0.013	0.009
HCMC	0.604	0.557	0.554	0.041	0.023	0.015
ROV	0.077	0.040	0.038	0.638	0.538	0.557
Total impact	0.744	0.621	0.618	0.72	0.574	0.581

Source: Calculating of authors

Table 4 shows that the spillover from domestic final demand to output and value added of the period 2015 - 2020 is lower than that of the period 2010 - 2015. In the previous period, the increase of 1 unit of final consumption (C) induced to output and value added was 1.84 and 0.71, but in the period 2015-2020 this coefficient was only 1.4 and 0.42. , spillover effects from export to output and value added also decreased compared to the previous period 1.8 and 0.57 compared to 1.42 and 0.32 respectively; the worst is investment when the spillover coefficient from investment (I) to output and income decreases from 2.2 and 0.6 to only 1.7 and 0.2; This shows that about 30% of investment does not go to production and the amount of investment to efficient production is also lower than in the previous period. The most basic thing is that the Keynesian supply curve gradually shifts to a vertical; all effects on the demand side do not increase output and production income but only increase trade deficit and inflation risks. This result shows that it is necessary to change the way of thinking from short-term Keynesian to long-term with the aim of increasing resources of the economy. Thus, if the investment is effective, it will make up for the reduced investment

Table 4. Output and value added induced by final demand (times)

Induced to Output				
	C	I	E*	
2010-2015	1.835	2.193	1.800	
2015-2020	1.435	1.717	1.423	
Induced to value added				
2010-2015	0.706	0.591	0.574	
2015-2020	0.420	0.199	0.315	

Source: Calculating of authors

I.V. Conclusion

Research results show that investment in most other regions is not as efficient as Ho Chi Minh City. Economic structure of Ho Chi Minh City shows that all factors of final demand are spillover to output and value added. Exports and value added are impressive; especially exports and government investments have a very high impact on the added value not only of HCMC but also of ROV.

Moreover, the calculation results show that when the final demand inside HCMC (including final consumption, investment and export) increases to 100 dong, it spreads to the internal added value. in Ho Chi Minh City about 89% and 11% spread to other areas. In which: Consumption in Ho Chi Minh City will spread to value added in other regions of the country by 17%, while investment and export of Ho Chi Minh City will spread to value added in other regions. the rest of the country is 8.8% and 8.7%. This is a very high spillover rate, showing the importance of Ho Chi Minh City's economy to the national economy.

Inter-regional analysis shows that the final demand factors of Ho Chi Minh City not only spill over to the city's production and income In Ho Chi Minh City, but also strongly spread to other regions of the country, this level of spread is 1.5 to 1.9 times, higher than that of other regions. An interesting point is that the spillover of

investment in fixed assets from the state capital has a high spillover rate to production in Ho Chi Minh City, which has a very impressive and higher spillover compared to other regions, while the spillover index of Ho Chi Minh City is 1.51, the region with the second highest index (Hanoi) is only 1.304. Thus, Ho Chi Minh City can be seen as a tractor for the development of the whole country. Growth in final demand (GDP) of Ho Chi Minh City is not only for Ho Chi Minh City itself but also for other regions of Vietnam.

The assuming that, if HCMC's investment increases by 10%, the GRDP of HCMC may increase by about 1.5% and the GDP of the whole country increase by about 0.8-1%. Economically, HCMC can be considered as a particularly important region that is the driving force behind the development of Vietnam's economy. If Ho Chi Minh City's growth slows down, it will not only have effect to itself, but will also have multiplier effects on other regions and the whole country in the following production cycles.

Therefore, the Government of Vietnam has issued Resolution 38/NQ-CP on the proposal to develop a Resolution of the National Assembly on piloting a number of specific mechanisms and policies for the development of Ho Chi Minh City.

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Appendix 1, Sectors

1	Crop
2	Breed
3	Other agricultural activities n.e.c. and services in agriculture
4	forestry
5	Seafood
6	Mining
7	Meat products and animal and vegetable fat production
8	Seafood processing
9	Processed and preserved vegetables and fruits
10	CB milk and products from milk
11	Milling and Producing Flour
12	Sugar, cocoa, tea, coffee and other food
13	Animal feed
14	Wine, beer and non-alcoholic beverages
15	Cigarettes
16	Yarn and textile products
17	Clothes
18	Fur skins and shoes
19	Wood (processed) and wood products
20	Paper and paper products
21	Printing and copying products of all kinds
22	Gasoline, oil and petroleum products
23	Chemicals and products from chemicals
24	Medicines, pharmaceutical chemicals and medicinal herbs
25	SP from rubber and plastic
26	Glass and glass products
27	Building materials
28	Iron, steel, cast iron
29	Other metal products remaining
30	Electronic components; Computers and computer peripherals
31	Machinery and equipment for radio, television, communication equipment, consumer electronics products
32	Other electronic products, generator motors, batteries and accumulators
33	Household electrical appliances, lighting equipment and electrical equipment
34	Machinery and equipment (except electrical equipment)
35	Cars and motor vehicles
36	Motorcycles, motorbikes and other means of transport
37	Other industrial products
38	Electricity
39	Production and distribution of water and gas
40	Build
41	Commercial
42	Passenger transport

43	Cargo
44	Postage and delivery
45	Lodging
46	Restaurant
47	Financial intermediary service
48	Real estate business and consulting activities
49	Scientific and technological activities
50	Services provided by activities of the Communist Party, socio-political organizations, state management of national security and defense; compulsory social security provided
51	Services of travel agents and tour operators; Support services related to tour promotion and organization
52	Education
53	Medical
54	Culture, sports, entertainment
55	Other services